

STUDENTS’ DIFFICULTIES IN SPEAKING ENGLISH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14209440>

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Abstract: *Speaking is considered one of the main skills of communication for English language learners. Students tend to face challenges through the process of learning and improving speaking skills. The current paper aims to study the difficulties students encounter in EFL-speaking classrooms and the major causes of these challenges.*

Keywords: *challenges, EFL classroom, speaking skill, psychological factors, critical thinking, accuracy and effectiveness.*

English is an international language which is spoken by most people around the world. In educational and professional field, English is mostly used for communication among them. In Uzbekistan, English is spoken as a foreign language and has become a core study which is taught at the level of elementary school to high school and up to university. The students of University are demanded to be able to use spoken English in the job-field when they conduct their job-field practice.

No-one argued that speaking skill is an important thing to carry out a conversation in the language. In accordance with this, students at High School who are prepared to be masters in the job field should be a master in speaking English as it is an international language [1]. It is urgent for them to know how to start a conversation, how to extend and how to close a conversation correctly with their peers, teachers and customers.

There are three areas of knowledge that students have to gain skills to be master in speaking, namely (1) language elements that consist of pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary, (2) the functions of language that deals with speaking performance in the form of transaction and interaction (3) the socio cultural norms such as turn-taking, rate of speech, length of pauses between speakers, relative role of participants, understanding how to take into account who is speaking to whom, in what circumstances, about what, and for what reason [2].

In line with these areas of knowledge, students strive to improve their ability to effectively communicate through speaking. They do not only know how to pronounce

a word, how to arrange words into a good sentence and how to enrich their mind with more vocabularies. Otherwise, they have to know the functions of language and the socio-cultural norms in order to communicate well with others. Additionally, [2] mentioned some non-linguistics elements which support speech to be clear, such as gestures, body language, intonations, facial expressions. In short, we can conclude that to master speaking skill is the most complex and most difficult. It is needed not only linguistics knowledge but also non linguistics aspects in order to convey the message correctly and clearly to the receiver of the message.

According to Brown [2] speaking is a productive skill that can be directly and empirically observed, those observations are invariably colored by the accuracy and effectiveness of a test-takers listening skill, which necessarily compromises the reliability and validity of an oral production test. In accordance with this statement students' speaking skill can be observed for accuracy and effectiveness.

During speaking skill is a productive skill, students have to create their own language to delivery their opinion or when they do communication with others. As a productive skill, speaking skill should be more practiced in order to train students express their ideas. It is not to consume other's language but to produce a language. Relate to produce a language, students should be master in speaking skill. Speaking skills consist of fluency, vocabulary, pronunciation and grammar. It is also supported by gesture, confidence, and motivation. Furthermore, Brown [3] argued that speaking is an interactive process of constructing meaning that involves producing, receiving and processing information. In relation to processing information, students have to understand the spoken language they get. They will process the information easily when they are master in linguistics competency. At least, they are familiar with the words or sound they hear.

As a tool of communication, speaking skill plays a vital role in interaction with others in real life. Mastering speaking skill indicates who the speaker is in the society. Chomsky [4] gives definition about the ability as a skill, power, competence, knowledge. Speaking ability is the competence or a power of speaking in delivering a conversation. The receiver of the message will understand the conversation when the speaker speaks clearly. Speaking clearly means the speaker speaks in grammatical rule, pronounces it properly and uses a proper word. In addition, it is supported by mimicry, intonation and gestures so conversation can be understood well and clearly. There is no misunderstanding due to the lack of speaking ability. Furthermore, Richard categorized the function of speaking in real life into three classes namely speaking skill as an interaction, speaking skill as a transaction and speaking skill as a performance. With regard to the function of speaking, it can be defined that speaking is people's life. They can interact in social life, they can make transaction to fulfil

their needs and they can perform their capability in society by speaking. Modern trends courage an increasing number of people to discuss various dilemmas that concern our society in some way; in this regard, one should acknowledge that an alarmingly large number of students face challenges on a daily basis when confronted with difficult topics such as politics, medicine, global issues, and many more to mention. While it may initially appear that this is due to a lack of ideas, experience, or a narrow-minded perspective, a closer examination of the root issue reveals that the challenges students face when discussing complex topics can stem from a variety of factors. Here are some reasons why students may struggle with engaging in discussions on challenging subjects:

1. **Lack of Knowledge and Understanding:** Students may struggle with complex topics because they lack sufficient knowledge and understanding of the subject matter. Without a solid foundation of information, it can be difficult to contribute meaningfully to a discussion. Additionally, a limited understanding of scientific terminology or technical jargon related to specific topics aggravates the issue." "The problem could have been more easily solved if mental, social, psychological, and behavioral concerns were not so prevalent. However, the prevalence of these concerns makes it more difficult to address the issue at hand. The lack of critical thinking and being trapped in a conformist mindset, as well as the fear of going against societal norms and expressing unique ideas, prevents Uzbek youth from challenging traditional beliefs and breaking free from limiting stereotypes and prejudices.

2. **Fear of Being Judged:** Students may hesitate to engage in discussions on challenging topics because they fear being judged by their peers or teachers. This fear of criticism can inhibit their ability to express their thoughts and opinions openly.

3. **Lack of Critical Thinking Skills:** Discussing complex topics often requires critical thinking skills to analyze information, evaluate arguments, and form well-reasoned opinions. Students who have not developed these skills may find it challenging to participate in discussions effectively.

4. **Emotional Responses:** Some challenging topics, such as politics or social issues, can evoke strong emotions in students. These emotional responses may hinder their ability to engage in a rational and constructive discussion.

5. **Limited Exposure to Diverse Perspectives:** Students may struggle with complex topics if they have had limited exposure to diverse perspectives and viewpoints. Engaging with a range of opinions can help students develop a more nuanced understanding of complex issues.

6. **Lack of Confidence:** Students may lack the confidence to participate in discussions on challenging topics, especially if they feel intimidated by more

outspoken classmates or if they doubt their own abilities to contribute meaningfully to the conversation.

7. Inadequate Support and Guidance: Students may face challenges discussing complex topics if they do not receive adequate support and guidance from teachers or mentors. Effective facilitation and encouragement can help students feel more comfortable engaging in discussions on challenging subjects. The above given diagram portrays how different approaches can be applied to overcome speaking barriers among language learners. For instance, sufficient stock of topic related vocabulary, ability to have you own standpoint as well as being able to accept opinions unlike your own ones.

Speaking difficulties are difficulties that make someone lack in speaking proficiency. Oxford Dictionary (4th edition) defines difficulties as not easy, needing effort or skill, full of problems, causing trouble, difficult to do or to understand. We can say that speaking difficulties are full of problems that appear when someone speak or to understand the spoken language.

Similarly, to the definition above, Doris and Jessica [5] argued that language problems may become the obstacles reason for the students to improve their language performance. Language problem covers probably because poor in grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation. Those problems belong to linguistics factors. Other problem that may come while speaking are lack of confidence, fear of making mistake, feeling shy, anxiety, lack of motivation. Those problems belong to psychological factors. Juhana [8] in her study she concludes that some psychological factors such as fear of making mistake, shyness, anxiety and the like that hinder students while speaking English in class. It means that student’s success in speaking performance is not only caused by lack of linguistics knowledge but also caused by psychological factors. Fitriani in their study found that 20.70% difficulties in speaking caused by psycholinguistics factors then followed by linguistics factors namely 19.59%. Students need effort to have speaking competence. Even more, to learn foreign that the problem that students have in speaking aspect, such as vocabulary, pronunciation, grammar and fluency. Various study has shown the difficulties that students have in speaking English which were conducted by [8] They found some problems that cause students to fail in speaking competence. Speaking problems are problems that hamper students to speak. These problems are obstacles for students that make them failure in English speaking competence. states that speaking is one skill selecting appropriate words and sentence according to the proper social setting, audience, situation and subject matter. Thus, in speaking activity, someone need to master speaking skill aspect that consist of linguistics and non-linguistics.

Doris and Jessica [5] stated that language problems serve as one of the important reason behind poor academic performance. Those problems are linguistics aspect such as lack of vocabulary, grammatical error and poor pronunciation and psychological aspect, such as lack of self-confidence, shyness, fear of making mistake, anxiety, mother tongue language and lack of motivation to learn. All this aspect cause students fail in speaking English competence.

These difficulties in speaking skill are also supported by the findings of the research conducted by Heriansyah [7] found five problems and the cause such as: 1) not being brave to speak. The cause is being afraid of making mistakes and feeling not confident to speak. 2) Not being confident to speak, the cause is being afraid of making errors. 3) Being afraid of speaking was caused by being afraid of making errors. 4) Nervous to speak and 5) not used to talking in the classroom because I was afraid of making errors. In conclusion, the difficulties faced by the students appear from themselves. Not being confident, feeling shy, and feeling afraid of making errors are psychological factors which hamper students' ability to speak. These factors can be solved by creating an English club, teachers always encourage students to speak, more practice with the peer students etc.

It is important for educators to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment that encourages students to explore and discuss complex topics openly. By addressing these challenges and providing students with the necessary tools and resources, educators can help empower students to engage meaningfully in discussions on a wide range of important issues.

To conclude, it is worth to note that all above mentioned facts indeed contribute to develop learners' oral speech and each of these aspects need practice, hard work and persistence.

REFERENCES

1. Amelia, M. & Komariah E. (2017). Investigating English Speaking Skill Problems Encountered by Students at Islamic Modern Boarding School. READ publication,119-126
2. Brown, H.D. (2001). Teaching by Principles. An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.
3. Brown, H.D. (2003). Language Assessment Principle and Classroom Practice. New York. Longman.
4. Chomsky, N. (1965). Persistent Topic in Linguistics Theory. SAGE Journals.
5. Doris & Jessica. (2007).Journal Deaaries Fitria, RW.A Study on the students English Speaking problems in speaking performance.

6. Fulcher. G., Reiter. R. M. (2003). Task Difficulty in Speaking. SAGE Journals. Research articles
7. Heriansyah, H. (2012). Speaking problems faced by the English department students of Syiah Kuala University. *Lingua Didaktika: Journal Bahasa dan Pembelajaran Bahasa*, 6(1), 37-44.
8. Juhana (2012) Psychological Factors That Hinder Students from Speaking in English Class The English Department, Indonesia Open University- *Journal of Education and Practice* www.iiste.org Vol 3, No 12, 2012
9. Kagan. S., Kagan. M. (2009). Teaching to Training Teachers Through Cooperative Learning.
10. Lynch, D., Hennessy, J. (2017). I Choose to Become A Teacher. *Asia- Pacific Journal of Education* 45 (2) p. 106-125
11. Рузметова Д. А. Об экономической потенциальной лексике //Молодой ученый. – 2012. – №. 4. – С. 455-457.
12. Adilbekovna R. D. Challenges in Teaching English as a Specific Purpose //Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 93-97.
13. D.A. Ruzmetova, Z.N. Abdullayeva INGLIZ TILIDAGI ILMIY TERMINLARNI IDROK ETISHNING PSIXOLOGIK JIHATLARI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2024. №CSPU Conference
14. Рузметова Д.А. ТГПУ имени Низами г. Ташкент, Узбекистан. Об изучении текстов по специальности международный научный журнал «Вестник науки» № 2 (23) т.2. февраль 2020 г.